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Compressive Strength of Cement-Based Composites Using Machine Learning Models

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to compare the compressive strength of cellulose nanofibrils (CNFs) reinforced concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar utilizing machine learning models for prediction before construction. To obtain this goal, the ten supervised regression ML models were executed. The datasets with an experimental foundation consisting of 266, 233, and 196 data points for cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete respectively were set and split into training and testing groups for the models' execution. There were seven input parameters: cement, water, CNFs, superplasticizer, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, and age, and one output parameter: compressive strength f_c . The results declared that seven models for cement paste, six models for cement mortar, and eight models for concrete had a strong ability to predict compressive strength. According to the sensitivity analysis, water and cement were the parameters with the largest impacts on predicting the CNFs reinforced cement-based composites, while coarse aggregate was the smallest. It can be concluded that Extreme Gradient Boosting Regression, Gradient Boosting Regression, and Random Forest models for concrete; Extreme Gradient Boosting Regression, Gradient Boosting Regression, and Decision Tree models for cement paste; and K-Nearest Neighbors, Bagging Regressor, and Random Forest models for cement mortar were the best prediction models.

1 | Introduction

Concrete is the second-most consumed material in the world, after water. Cement production ranks third globally in terms of industrial energy consumption and is the 2nd largest commercial radiator of CO₂, contributing to around 7% of global emissions [1]. A new environmentally friendly substance that is being introduced to the construction industry offers a promising new route towards sustainable development [2, 3]. Another related trend is the use of additives made of nanomaterials [3, 4].

Cement-based composites' short- and long-term properties have emerged and continue to show a great deal of promise for advancement through nanotechnology [5]. An interdisciplinary branch of science and engineering called nanotechnology is concerned with identifying and working with materials with sizes ranging from one to one hundred nanometers [6]. Since concrete is the most popular building material in the world and because the construction industry wants to use nanotechnology to reduce its environmental impact, it has developed sophisticated techniques for concrete design that allow for the creation of various

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types of concrete that contain various mineral admixtures [7]. The use of specialized concrete has significantly increased during the past few years, including reinforced concrete strengthened with cellulose nanoparticles. Cellulose nanofibrils (CNFs) are hydrophilic biodegradable nanoparticles (typically, less than 0.2 mm in length and 20–50 nm in width) that can be extracted from various plants, trees, and recycled paper stock. Their low density, low toxicity, relatively low cost, high aspect ratio, and high specific surface enable functionalization [3]. In addition to helping to reduce CO₂ emissions [8], the increasing use of concrete admixtures, which are made from waste products from other industrial or agricultural operations, lays the groundwork for so-called sustainable development and the creation of green buildings [9, 10]. By the advancement of computer technology, the involvement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques in the construction industry has been increased since the last few decades. These AI techniques, especially machine learning (ML) have not only introduced easy and quick ways of construction development but also have eliminated the cost and efforts of sample preparation and strength testing by performing practical tests on cement-based composites.

In this instance, the use of machine learning and artificial intelligence approaches to forecast concrete's compressive strength is growing. Regression, classification, and clustering are supervised and unsupervised machine learning tasks that can be accomplished using these approaches [11]. As a result, with the advancement of ML approaches, estimating the compressive strength and other mechanical parameters is now straightforward [12]. Specifically, the compressive strength of CNFs reinforced concrete can be ascertained by applying certain approaches such as machine learning regression techniques, which pick up from the intake dataset and produce very precise outcomes. Currently, ANNs, ensemble methods, and generalized additive models are among the ML techniques used to estimate the compressive strength of CNFs concrete [13]. Machine learning techniques, which are very systematic in terms of computing and time development, can be used to analyze large data sets [14]. This leads to reducing the error rates to nearly zero levels as a result of speedier and more precise outcomes. This produces faster and more accurate results, bringing error rates down to nearly nonexistent levels.

However, we must be able to foretell the concrete strength based on the early strength data in order to speed up the construction process. Therefore, an accurate and timely prediction of concrete strength would be crucial. For instance, it might present an opportunity to adjust the mix proportions accustomed to prevent places where concrete does not deliver the necessary design strength or by preventing concrete that is excessively strong, as well as to ensure more economical use of raw materials and fewer construction collapses, which would lower construction costs [15]. As a result, there has been extensive research in the prediction of concrete strength, and several studies have been conducted. Numerous research projects have been conducted in this field like Marani et al. utilized machine learning techniques to predict the compressive strength of cementitious composites that integrate phase change materials, demonstrating the potential of AI in construction materials engineering [15]. Kheder et al. developed a mathematical model to predict cement compressive strength at 7 and 28 days, providing a method that estimates

results within 24 h [16]. Zain et al. used multiple regression analysis to predict the compressive strength of high-performance concrete, offering an accurate predictive model for the construction industry [17]. Zain et al. proposed a model to predict the splitting tensile strength of high-performance concrete, complementing existing models for compressive strength [18]. Tsvilis and Parissakis presented a mathematical model aimed at predicting the strength of cement, contributing to more precise strength estimations in construction materials [19]. Zelić et al. introduced a model to predict the compressive strength of cement-silica fume blends, highlighting the influence of silica fume on cement performance [20]. Akkurt et al. applied fuzzy logic to predict cement compressive strength, showcasing an innovative approach that deals with uncertainty in material properties [21]. Cavaleri et al. investigate the use of convolution-based ensemble learning algorithms to estimate the bond strength of corroded reinforced concrete, demonstrating their effectiveness and highlighting the influence of corrosion level, concrete compressive strength, and other factors on bond strength [22]. Nguyen et al. propose a heuristic algorithm-based semi-empirical formula for estimating the compressive strength of normal and high-performance concrete, demonstrating its accuracy and interpretability compared to machine learning models [23]. Cavaleri et al. explore the use of artificial neural networks to model the surface roughness of electro-discharge machined surfaces, showcasing the potential of neural networks for predicting and optimizing EDM processes [24]. Ashrafian et al. propose a machine learning model to predict the compressive strength of sustainable lightweight structural concrete (SLSC) containing oil palm by-product, demonstrating its accuracy and highlighting the influence of key variables on strength [25]. Asteris et al. develop a hybrid ensemble machine learning model to predict concrete compressive strength, combining multiple machine learning models and an artificial neural network, resulting in higher predictive accuracy compared to individual models [26]. Alkayem et al. explore the use of machine learning and deep learning techniques to predict the properties of concrete and fiber-reinforced concrete at high temperatures, discussing the advantages, challenges, and future directions of these approaches [27].

There have been numerous attempts to develop an appropriate mathematical model that can accurately forecast the strength of concrete at different ages [22–25]. Technical workers frequently experiment with different mix proportions to produce concrete of the desired and appropriate strength. This time-consuming process wastes materials and raises the price of producing concrete [26–28]. Therefore, ML models are designed to save time and cut down on design costs. It should be mentioned that numerous research studies have been conducted to estimate the compressive strength utilizing ML approaches for unique forms of concrete, including fiber-reinforced concrete, self-consolidating concrete, recycled aggregate concrete, and ultra-high performance concrete. Due to the huge number of mixed components [29, 30], innovative concretes demand complex mixture design [28], which gave rise to complex non-linear relationships [29].

Therefore, it is crucial to configure the model and tune its hyper-parameters in order to maximize the performance of the applied method for a given task [30]. Due to their improved performance with fewer variables and over-fittings, these ensembles are preferred. Using 1030 data sets and nine variables, Kaloop

et al. [31] developed a gradient tree boosting algorithm to assess the compressive strength of HPC. When the correlation coefficient and mean absolute error (MAE) were 0.965 and 0.037 MPa, respectively, researchers discovered that ensembles could predict the concrete strength with more precision. Overall, it has been demonstrated that ML approaches are effective at foretelling the compressive strength of several unique concrete types.

ML algorithms can be used to conduct a parametric research of mixing proportions for various types of concretes without significant experimental programs because they are most effective in data analysis. Additionally, a study like this one using ML models decreases material waste, the requirement for human resources, and the high expense of labor-intensive trial mixes. However, rather than being dependent on the hydration proceeding and microstructure of concrete, the success of ML models heavily depends on the sample dataset and hyperparameters. The number of datasets for model training and validation should be chosen appropriately using hyperparameters, although there is currently no fixed rule for doing so [32]. As a result, it is difficult to evaluate the effectiveness of ML techniques used in comparable experiments. The researchers employ a variety of machine learning approaches and algorithms to target distinct prediction goals at different dataset points. Table 1 is a list of some of them.

With the development of concrete technology, analytical models unsuccessful to rationalize the difficulty of strength-affecting factors and figure out less precise results. Although Machine Learning (ML) techniques have manifested superior correctness for predicting the mixture divisions and mechanical properties of novel concrete with complex cementitious material [34–37]. The chemical and physical complexity of concrete's ingredients, including cement paste, aggregates, and additives is obvious. It is therefore extremely difficult to develop a strength prediction model using an analytical or mathematical approach that simultaneously takes into account the effect of significant influencing factors such as cement's chemical and physical properties, aggregate bond strength, aggregate properties, cement hydration, etc. [38]. Due to ML's impressive ability to solve complex problems in the construction industry, including quality management, design optimizations, fracture mechanics, structural health monitoring, and risk control, researchers have recently started using machine learning techniques to predict concrete strength [39]. However, traditional statistical techniques like linear and non-linear regression analyses, which have demonstrated satisfactory prediction accuracy, can be used to model the correlation between concrete strength and mixture contents. As a result, ML is not well known for estimating the compressive strength of conventional concrete [40]. In order to estimate the compressive strength of cement mortar, cement paste, and concrete enhanced with cellulose nanofibers, our preprint evaluates ten machine learning models' prediction capabilities [2].

This study aims to investigate and assess the predictive power of different machine learning models for predicting the compressive strength of CNF-reinforced cement-based composites, such as concrete, mortar, and paste. By applying a wide variety of supervised regression models to an extensive dataset created from experimental data, this study makes a distinctive contribution to the body of knowledge by enabling a reliable comparison of model performance across various material compositions.

Sensitivity analysis is integrated to provide additional insight into the relative importance of important input factors and to aid in the optimization of CNF-reinforced composites. The results show that certain models, such as DT, GBR, and XGBR for cement paste, KNN, BR, and RF for cement mortar, and XGBR, GBR, and RF for concrete, offer better prediction accuracy than others. This lays the groundwork for optimizing material compositions before building. This work lays the groundwork for future developments in the predictive modeling of composite materials and shows that machine learning models are feasible in the construction industry.

Consequently, the materials and methods, detail of the dataset, training and testing, ML algorithms, and performance matrices are provided in Section 2. Subsequently, Section 3 presents a comprehensive description of the results and discussion of the correlation coefficient analysis, descriptive analysis of variables, outlier analysis, multivariate analysis, and density curve analysis. Besides, the evaluation of the predictive capability of each ML model and sensitivity analysis is also included. The conclusions are summarized in Section 4.

2 | Materials and Methods

The predictive capabilities of RF, LR, SVR, ABR, KNN, BR, GBR, XGBR, DT, and PDT algorithms in estimating the compression strength of cement paste, mortar, and concrete reinforced with carbon nanofibers were comprehensively evaluated. This evaluation involved the utilization of various performance metrics, including coefficient of determination (R^2), mean square error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), subsequent to the stages of dataset acquisition and preprocessing. Additionally, the K-fold cross-validation technique was employed to compare the R^2 values across all test datasets. Each model was run to predict the compression strength of CNFs reinforced cement-based composites: cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete. Nevertheless, the best statistic for judging algorithms is thought to be the coefficient of determination value, or R^2 . Furthermore, if the value range falls between 0.60 and 0.75, the R^2 result is deemed appropriate and practicable; if the estimation range falls between 0.75 and 0.90, the model is good and wanted; and if the R^2 result is larger than 0.95, it signals exceptional projection. On the other hand, R^2 values less than 0.60 denote poor performance, which is unacceptable [1, 41]. To examine and investigate the contribution of each independent variable, sensitivity analysis was ultimately carried out. The technical flowchart followed to obtain research objectives is elaborated in Figure 1.

2.1 | Experimental Dataset

The dataset collected throughout the experiment contained the observations of samples including 266 cement paste, 233 mortar, and 196 concrete reinforced with CNFs [42]. In total, 695 samples of CNFs-reinforced cement-based composites were included in the dataset compiled during the investigation. The dataset was summarized in Table 2 along with the quantity of data Number of Datapoints, and its proportion "Percentage", and "Reference".

TABLE 1 | Prediction properties applying various techniques [33].

No	Techniques	Abbreviation	Attributes	Output	Reinforced fiber
1	Support vector machine	SVM	144	Compressive strength	Fly Ash
2	Gene expression programming	GEP	303	Bearing capacity of concrete-filled steel tube column	—
3	Data envelopment analysis	DEA	114	Compressive strength Slump test L-box test V-funnel test	Fly Ash
4	Gene expression programming, artificial neural network, decision tree	GEP, ANN, DT	642	Surface chloride concentration	Fly Ash
5	Support vector machine	SVM	—	Compressive strength	Fly Ash
6	Support vector machine	SVM	115	Slump test, L-box test, V-funnel test, Compressive strength	Fly Ash
7	Gene expression programming	GEP	351	Compressive strength	GGBS
8	Gene expression programming	GEP	54	Compressive strength	NZ (natural zeolite)
9	Gene expression programming	GEP	357	Compressive strength	—
10	Random forest and gene expression programming	RF and GEP	357	Compressive strength	—
11	Artificial neuron network	ANN	205	Compressive strength	Fly Ash, GGBFS, SF, RHA
12	Intelligent rule-based enhanced multiclass support vector machine and fuzzy rules	IREMSVM-FR with RSM	114	Compressive strength	Fly Ash
13	Random forest	RF	131	Compressive strength	Fly Ash GGBFS
14	Individual and ensemble algorithm	GEP, DT, and bagging ANN	270	Compressive strength	Fly Ash
15	Individual with ensemble modeling	Bagging and boosting	1030	Compressive strength	Fly Ash
16	Multivariate	MV	21	Compressive strength	Crumb rubber SF
17	Gene expression programming	GEP	277	Axial capacity	—
18	Adaptive neuro fuzzy inference system	ANFIS with ANN	7	Compressive strength	POFA
19	Ensemble machine learning models	RF, KNN, GB, XGB	515	Compressive strength	Self-compacting concrete
20	Artificial neuron network	ANN	1030	Compressive strength	Highperformance concrete
21	Artificial neuron network	ANN	187	Compressive strength, slump	High strength concrete
22	Regression, neural network and ANFIS models	Regression, ANN	96	Compressive strength	No-slump concrete
23	Artificial neural networks	ANN	80	Unconfined compressive strength	Cement-stabilized sandy soil
24	Decision tree, Artificial neural network, Bagging, and gradient boosting	DT, ANN, GB	207	Compressive strength	Concrete at high temperature
25	Artificial neural network	ANN	117	Compressive strength	Silica fume and natural zeolite
26	Adaptive boosting	—	1030	Compressive strength	Blast furnace slag and fly ash
27	Artificial neural network	ANN	243	Compressive strengths and the durability test	Slag and recycled aggregate concrete

The selection of datasets addresses the application of cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) in reinforcing cement-based composites. The dataset describes how cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) are used to reinforce cement-based composites. The study incorporated cement, water, carbon nanofibers (CNFs), superplasticizer, fine and coarse aggregates, age, and seven other characteristics as input variables. The output parameter under investigation was

the compressive strength (f_c). Utilizing the Jupyter Notebook within the Anaconda Python software environment, these parameters were analyzed to ascertain correlations within the dataset and validate the predictive capability of the model. It also displayed the graphical depiction. It was clear that the performance of the model was highly influenced by the independent factors [33, 51].

FIGURE 1 | Technical flowchart followed to obtain research objective.

TABLE 2 | Experimental dataset.

Sr. No.	Number of datapoints	Percentage %	References
1	216	31.10	Takasi 2019 [43]
2	147	21.15	Chopra et al., 2015 [35]
3	142	20.43	Kolour, 2019 [3]
4	80	11.51	Kamasamudram, 2019 [9]
5	30	4.32	Oh et al., 2022 [44]
6	21	3.02	Mejdoub et al., 2017 [45]
7	18	2.59	Onuaguluchi et al., 2014 [46]
8	15	2.16	Hisseine et al., 2019 [47]
9	12	1.73	Da Silva et al., 2021 [48]
10	6	0.86	da Costa Correia et al., 2019 [49]
11	5	0.72	Barnat-Hunek et al., 2019 [10]
12	3	0.43	Alzoubi et al., 2020 [50]
Total	695	100.00	

2.2 | Dataset Division

Machine learning techniques depend on benchmarking the dataset by splitting it into train and test subsets [52–55]. After the model was constructed utilizing the train set of cement-based composites, cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete, the testing set of data was used to evaluate the model's performance. The training dataset subset was utilized for model development, whereas the testing dataset was employed to assess the algorithm's predictive accuracy regarding the compressive

strength of cement-based composites reinforced with carbon nanofibers (CNFs), including cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete. Because of this, in this work, 70% of each dataset was used to train the model, and the remaining 30% was randomly selected to test the compressive strength of cement-based composites made by CNFs. For the cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete datasets, the same process was repeated.

2.3 | Model Development

The current investigation utilized ten supervised regression machine learning algorithms (RF, LR, SVR, ABR, KNN, BR, XGBR, DT, PDT, and GBR) to determine the compressive strength of various materials including cement-based composites, cement paste, cement mortar, and carbon nanofiber-reinforced concrete. Following the preparation of the data, each dataset was imported into the Jupyter notebook, and the regression learning procedures were started with the input and output variables. Thirty percent of the data was used for testing, while the remaining 70% was used to create the prediction model. The random search method is employed to explore the hyperparameter space efficiently. The parameters developed for each algorithm were listed in Table 3.

2.4 | Model's Performance

The five statistical performance criteria R^2 , MSE, RMSE, MAE, and MAPE were applied to assess the strength and accuracy of the supervised regression ML algorithms that were suggested to ascertain the compressive strength f_c (MPa) of CNFs cement-based composites, cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete. The R^2 , MSE, RMSE, MAE, and MAPE can be determined, correspondingly, by using Equations (1–5) [1, 2, 56, 57].

TABLE 3 | Parameters specification to develop model.

Model	Parameters
RF	n_estimators = 100; criterion = 'squared_error'; max_depth = None; min_samples_split = 2; min_samples_leaf = 1; min_weight_fraction_leaf = 0.0; max_features = 1.0; and random_state = None
LR	fit_intercept = True; copy_X = True; n_jobs = None; and positive = False. SVR: kernel = 'rbf'; degree = 3; gamma = 'scale'; coef0 = 0.0; tol = 0.001; and cache_size = 200
GBR	loss = 'squared_error'; learning_rate = 0.1; n_estimators = 100; criterion = 'friedman_mse'; min_samples_split = 2; max_depth = 3; init = None; random_state = None; and validation_fraction = 0.1
ABR	n_estimators = 50; learning_rate = 1.0; loss = 'linear'; random_state = None KNN: n_neighbors = i where i was in range (1.45) n_neighbors = 2 got the best result; weights = 'uniform'; and leaf_size = 30
BR	n_estimators = 10; max_samples = 1.0; max_features = 1.0; random_state = None; and base_estimator = 'deprecated'
XGBR	base_score = 0.5; booster = 'gbtree'; learning_rate = 0.3; max_depth = 6; n_estimators = 100; and random_state = 0
DT	criterion = 'squared_error'; splitter = 'best'; max_depth = None; min_samples_split = 2; min_samples_leaf = 1; and random_state = None
PDT	criterion = 'squared_error'; splitter = 'best'; max_depth = None; min_samples_split = 2; min_samples_leaf = 1; and random_state = None

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum |(y_i - \hat{y}_i)| \quad (4)$$

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{100}{n} \sum \left| \frac{(y_i - \hat{y}_i)}{y_i} \right| \quad (5)$$

where $y_i = fc$ (dependent parameters), $\hat{y}_i = \text{CS}$ (estimated), $\bar{y}_i = \text{mean}$ (actual fc), and $n = \text{total attributes in dataset}$. The RMSE, MAE and compressive strength of carbon nanofibers (CNFs) reinforced cement-based composites, concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar was quantified in megapascals (MPa), while R^2 , and MAPE were expressed as percentages. Supervised regression models can be employed to predict the compressive strength of CNFs reinforced cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete. In this context, metrics such as MSE, MAPE, MAE, and RMSE serve as indicators of prediction accuracy [44, 50, 58], where smaller values of these metrics correspond to higher precision rates. Conversely, a higher R^2 value, the primary metric of the study, indicates a stronger correlation with accuracy, thereby suggesting greater predictive capability of the model [13].

3 | Results and Discussion

ML, the foremost perspective of artificial intelligence (AI) has been perceived as a novel and effective technology for the construction industry [1, 2, 59, 60]. Until now, many ML models have been developed by researchers to determine the chemical and mechanical properties of concrete reinforced with fibers, but there still remains a gap. Henceforth, within this investigation,

we assessed the prognostication of compressive strength pertaining to concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar reinforced with cellulose nanofibers, employing machine learning methodologies. Broadly speaking, outcomes from this study indicate that the Random Forest model emerges as the most proficient predictive model [61].

3.1 | Analysis of Correlation Coefficients

To evaluate the interdependence of factors, an exploratory data analysis (r) was carried out among the dependent variable (Y), compressive strength fc , and the input parameters (x), cement, water, CNFs, superplasticizers, fine aggregates, coarse aggregates, and age. The correlation ratio between the variables was shown by the obtained value of r ; the greater the value, the stronger the correlation. Every variable in this study was examined through Jupyter Notebook code. The specific instruction to assess the correlation heatmap was fed into the model during the computation of the correlation coefficient value. Equation (6) can be used to compute the correlation coefficient mathematically [62].

$$r = \frac{\sum [(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})]}{\sqrt{(x_i - \bar{x})^2 * (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (6)$$

where, $r = \text{Correlation coefficient}$, $x_i = \text{Input parameters}$, $\bar{x} = \text{Mean of input parameters}$, $y_i = fc$ (dependent parameters), $\bar{y} = \text{Mean of actual } fc$, $i = 1, \dots, n$, and $n = \text{Total dataset point}$ [13, 51, 63]. The paramount significance lies in the contribution of independent variables in constructing the model. The correlation coefficient, ranging from -1 to 1 , elucidates both the strength and direction of the relationship among variables. In essence, it indicates the extent of similarity in measurements across a dataset for two or more variables. The correlation coefficient is considered a perfect positive correlation if the value is 1 , zero correlation at 0 , and perfect negative correlation at -1 . These correlations can be characterized as follows: zero correlation, meaning there is no relationship between the variables; perfect positive correlation, meaning that when one variable changes, the other variables

FIGURE 2 | Cement paste correlation heatmap of the parameters.

change in the same way; perfect negative correlation, meaning that when one variable changes, the other variables change in the opposite way. No discernible reciprocal relationship exists between the two independent variables, as can be shown from the observation that the correlation coefficient value of any two variables, with the exception of identical variables, is not 1 [2, 64]. It demonstrates that the independent variables contribute separately to the development of each model and are not multicollinear. Although some of the variables have shown strong positive correlation in cement-based composites and cement mortar, they still were not multicollinear. Figures 2–4 display the correlation heatmap between the input and output variables for cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete datasets respectively.

The heatmaps provide a visual representation of the strength and direction of the relationships between the variables [65–67]. In Figure 2, the cement paste correlation heatmap reveals a strong positive correlation between cement and water (0.84), indicating that an increase in cement content tends to be associated with an increase in water content [1]. This is due to the need to maintain a consistent water-cement ratio for proper hydration. Other variables like CNFs, superplasticizer, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, and age show weaker correlations with compressive strength. This suggests that these variables have less direct influence on the strength of cement paste compared to cement and water. The cement mortar correlation heatmap of Figure 3 shows multiple strong positive correlations, including: Cement-Water (0.91), Cement-Fine Aggregate (0.89), Cement-Superplasticizer (0.88), Fine Aggregate-Water (0.81). While similar to cement paste, other variables like CNFs, superplasticizer, and coarse aggregate show weaker correlations with compressive strength. Also, the concrete heatmap in Figure 4 reveals a moderate

positive correlation between cement and water (0.79), indicating a similar relationship as observed in cement paste and mortar. Other variables like CNFs, superplasticizer, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, and age show weaker correlations with compressive strength. Overall, cement and water consistently show the strongest positive correlations with compressive strength across all three datasets. This aligns with the well-established understanding that the water-cement ratio is a critical factor influencing concrete strength. The weaker correlations observed for other variables suggest that while they contribute to the overall strength, their individual influence is relatively less significant compared to cement and water.

3.2 | Descriptive Analysis of Variables

Tables 4–6 present statistical summaries including the mean, median (50th percentile), 75th percentile, mode, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, sample variance, skewness, and sum of independent parameters: C (Kg/m³), W (Kg/m³), CNFs (Kg/m³), SP (Kg/m³), FA (Kg/m³), CA (Kg/m³), and A (day), alongside the dependent parameter: CS *fc* (MPa). These parameters were utilized to assess the compressive strength of carbon nanofiber (CNF) reinforced materials across datasets of cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete using supervised regression machine learning models. Skewness, a measure of asymmetry in a distribution, indicates the degree to which the distribution's left and right sides differ. A skewness value of zero suggests perfect symmetry, where the mean and median coincide, while positive or negative skewness indicates a deviation from this symmetry [43]. The mean of a positive-skewed distribution is almost always greater than its median. That is because extreme values affect the

FIGURE 3 | Cement mortar correlation heatmap of the parameters.

FIGURE 4 | Concrete correlation heatmap of the parameters.

TABLE 4 | Descriptive analysis of independent and dependent parameters of cement paste.

	Variables	Abbreviation	Count	Mean	25%	50%	75%	St. D	Min	Max	Sample variance	Skewness	Sum
Input	Cement (Kg/m ³)	C	266.00	487.74	411.80	506.34	548.13	66.14	325.00	566.04	4374.06	-0.64	129738.19
	Water (Kg/m ³)	W	266.00	179.10	148.25	183.75	210.00	46.21	12.29	262.5	2135.39	-0.86	47640.97
	Cellulose nanofiber (Kg/m ³)	CNFs	266.00	0.81	0.20	0.53	1.14	0.89	0.00	3.87	0.80	1.46	214.59
	Superplasticizer (Kg/m ³)	SP	266.00	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.22	0.00	10.50	1.49	3.71	120.94
	Age (Day)	A	266.00	29.44	7.00	28.00	28.00	24.25	1.00	90.00	588.01	1.33	7831.00
Output	Compressive strength <i>f_c</i> (MPa)	CS	266.00	53.53	41.78	55.70	64.75	15.75	7.5	97.9	247.97	-0.26	14240.18

TABLE 5 | Descriptive analysis of the independent and dependent parameters of cement mortar.

	Variables	Abbreviation	Count	Mean	25%	50%	75%	St. D	Min	Max	Sample variance	Skewness	Sum
Input	Cement (Kg/m ³)	C	233.00	209.75	160.06	206.11	218.96	87.57	126.17	566.44	7668.98	2.88	48873.82
	Water (Kg/m ³)	W	233.00	93.28	72.27	88.53	100.40	36.77	50.47	254.40	1352.18	2.74	21734.72
	Cellulose nanofiber (Kg/m ³)	CNFs	233.00	0.39	0.00	0.15	0.29	2.65	0.00	4000	7.04	14.53	89.80
	Superplasticizer (Kg/m ³)	SP	233.00	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.00	02.83	0.35	4.11	32.22
	Fine aggregate (Kg/m ³)	FA	233.00	256.82	215.40	254.90	320.92	328.81	197.45	1199.32	108116.88	3.28	83139.72
	Age (Day)	A	233.00	29.37	7.00	28.00	56.00	19.92	3.00	56.00	396.66	0.24	6844.00
Output	Compressive strength <i>f_c</i> (MPa)	CS	233.00	41.64	34.88	41.56	47.89	08.46	23.10	59.97	71.51	0.05	9701.26

TABLE 6 | Descriptive analysis of the independent and dependent parameters of concrete.

	Variables	Abbreviation	Count	Mean	25%	50%	75%	St. D	Min	Max	Sample variance	Skewness	Sum
Input	Cement (Kg/m ³)	C	196.00	440.62	400.00	425.00	475.00	78.34	260.00	580.00	6136.96	0.00	86360.95
	Water (Kg/m ³)	W	196.00	205.87	191.81	200.00	220.00	23.61	130.00	290.00	557.46	0.87	40351.19
	Cellulose nanofiber (Kg/m ³)	CNFs	196.00	0.083	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.00	3.87	0.11	8.51	16.29
	Superplasticizer (Kg/m ³)	SP	196.00	0.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.93	0.00	27.50	8.59	5.89	127.55
	Fine aggregate (Kg/m ³)	FA	196.00	597.50	485.88	549.13	590.75	216.40	175.50	1160.00	46830.70	1.89	117110.34
	Coarse aggregate (Kg/m ³)	CA	196.00	941.02	757.37	1049.75	1143.75	243.95	507.90	1253.75	59513.19	-0.55	184440.72
	Age (Day)	A	196.00	50.32	28.00	56.00	70.00	26.81	7.00	91.00	718.67	0.47	9863.00
Output	Compressive strength <i>f_c</i> (MPa)	CS	196.00	44.56	40.23	56.75	53.13	12.11	10.10	63.10	146.70	-1.14	8793.43

mean more than the median. In nearly all cases, the mean of a distribution with negative skew is lower than the median [1].

3.3 | Outlier Analysis of Variables

The identification of outlier values for the parameters in the datasets pertaining to concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar was conducted using commands within the Jupyter Notebook Python software. The graph showing the number of outliers in each variable for the cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete datasets was shown in Figures 5–7, respectively. It was observed that the outlier percentage for two variables—compressive strength and fine aggregates was—only 2% and 1%, respectively, and for four parameters—cement, water, coarse aggregate, and age was—zero. This was an example of an acceptable dataset [1, 2]. The outlier proportion for only two parameters cellulose—nanofibers and superplasticizers was—almost equal to 11, which is extremely low. However, 75% of the parameters did not have an outlier; this tiny percentage had no effect on the dataset's ability to predict the outcome. Figure 7 displayed the outstanding outlier results for the concrete dataset as compared to the cement paste and cement mortar datasets in Figures 5

and 6, respectively. It can be analyzed that the superplasticizer variable had shown 7% upper outliers. All other variables had displayed 0% outliers, except CNFs (1%) and CS (1%). The upper outlier percentage for cement paste dataset in Figure 7 has described 26% and 18% for CNFs and SP, respectively. In Figure 8 it can be observed that the upper outlier percentage for SP and FA had 5% and only 2% for CNFs.

3.4 | Multivariate Analysis of Variables

The multivariate analysis was conducted to study the distribution of variables. The multivariate analysis of input and output parameters, which delineates the density and frequency distribution of each parameter in constructing the model, is depicted in Figures 8–10. These figures illustrate the histograms corresponding to cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete, respectively. In the multivariate analysis of the concrete dataset, the variables C, W, FA, CA, A, and CS *f_c* had shown normal symmetrical distribution with very little skewness, while CNFs and superplasticizer displayed right skewness [1]. The multivariate analysis results of this research concrete dataset were almost identical (Figure 10). The cement, age, and compressive strength of the cement paste

FIGURE 5 | Outliers of cement paste dataset.

dataset had expressed normal symmetrical distribution with less skewness, but CNFs and superplasticizer manifested right skewness, and water presented weak left skewness in Figure 8. In the end, Figure 9 demonstrated that cement, water, age, and compressive strength f_c had symmetrical distribution with less skewness.

3.5 | Density Curve of Variables

To deeply analyze and more clearly understand the strength and capability of cement-based composites, concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar datasets, the pair plot graphs were drawn

through commands in the Jupyter Notebook Python software as shown in Figures 11–13. From the density curve, it is evident that the result was satisfactory [1], with less correlation, smooth flow, and non-multicollinearity. Figures 11–13 presented the density curve pair plot graphs of cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete, respectively.

Density plots, also called histograms, are the diagonal elements of each matrix, and they display the distribution of each individual variable. These shed light on each parameter's data distribution and skewness. A density plot with two peaks (a bimodal distribution) in the cement paste figure suggests that the variable has two main ranges of values. Every pair of variables is shown as a

FIGURE 6 | Outliers of cement mortar dataset.

FIGURE 7 | Outliers of concrete dataset.

FIGURE 8 | Cement paste multivariate analysis of each variable.

scatterplot in the off-diagonal elements. Every scatterplot shows the relationship between two variables. There may be little or no association if the points are widely scattered. There could be a substantial association between the two variables depending on whether they trend in a linear or nonlinear manner. A scatterplot of water versus compressive strength that displays a linear trend indicates a relationship between the two variables.

The distribution of every variable is shown on the diagonal in Figure 11. The distribution of the cement variable is unimodal, while the superplasticizer variable may exhibit a more skewed distribution. Pairwise relationships are displayed in scatterplots below the diagonal. An underlying pattern may be revealed if we identify any clusters or tendencies. Also, a significant relationship between cement content and compressive strength may be seen. Figure 12 illustrates this similarly to cement paste. However, as mortar usually contains additional modifiers in addition to fine particles, we might find distinct patterns. There is a substantial correlation between the fine aggregate content and other input factors, such as compressive strength. Figure 13's coarse aggregate-filled concrete adds even more unpredictability.

The correlation coefficient or data visualization is conducted to investigate the multi-collinearity between two variables. The correlation coefficient value of not any two different variables should be -1 to 1 [1, 13, 45, 68]. Ahmad et al. stated in their research that the correlation coefficient of some of the variables were (0.75 and 0.74) higher [55]. Also Jesus et al. proved that

some features of the heatmap of the self-compacting concrete had shown average correlation [13]. In this study, we observed that the cement paste dataset observations has shown less than 0.80 correlation. And the maximum correlation value for cement mortar dataset was 0.88. The descriptive analysis for concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar datasets were listed to explore the quantities of input and output variables. Kolour, H.H. reports the impact of cellulose nanofibrils on cement-based composites, and investigation into the maximum, minimum, mean, median, and standard deviation for compressive strength after examining the mechanical parameters with an emphasis on variability [3]. A. Nafees et al. give comprehensive statistical summaries of compressive strength, including extreme values and spread, using a variety of machine learning models to forecast the mechanical properties of silica fume-based green concrete [12].

Feng et al. employed an adaptive boosting approach to forecast concrete's compressive strength, with statistical measures provided to indicate the range and central tendencies of the dataset used for training and testing the models [13]. de-Prado-Gil et al. apply ensemble machine learning models to predict the strength of self-compacting concrete using recycled aggregates, describing the distribution of experimental data through maximum, minimum, median, and variability measures [14]. In order to forecast the compressive strength of concrete subjected to high temperatures, Ahmad et al. conducted a comparative analysis of supervised machine learning algorithms [34]. They presented summary statistics of the data for the purpose of evaluating

FIGURE 9 | Cement mortar multivariate analysis of each variable.

the model. Ahmad et al. use ensemble methods to forecast the compressive strength of fly ash-based concrete, and they include statistical descriptions of the dataset to validate the predictions made by the models [51]. Hassan and El-Hag used a two-layer ensemble-based soft voting classifier to predict transformer oil interfacial tension, and the study includes statistical measures to evaluate the model's performance [56]. The evaluation of compressive strength factors using machine learning provides a detailed statistical analysis, including max, min, mean, and deviation for the concrete samples examined by Jha et al. [57]. Regression, neural networks, and ANFIS models were used in a comparative study by Sobhani et al. to predict the compressive strength of no-slump concrete. Descriptive statistics were used to evaluate the accuracy of the models [44]. Utilizing neural networks, Öztaş et al. forecast the compressive strength and slump of high-strength concrete while verifying the robustness of the model by statistical measures such as maximum, minimum, and standard deviation [50]. This study comprehensively analyzed various statistical parameters including the mean,

median, quartiles, mode, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, sample variance, skewness, and sum concerning the inputs and outputs within concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar datasets, yielding valuable insights.

An outlier denotes an observational data point situated beyond the general trend or distribution pattern [42, 55]. In order to examine the outliers for the concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar datasets, the outlier's command was executed in the Jupyter Notebook software. The four parameters outlier percentage: cement, water, coarse aggregate, and age were zero, and two parameters: fine aggregates and compressive strength was only 1% and 2%, respectively, depicting a reasonable dataset [1]. The outstanding outlier results were found for the concrete dataset as compared to cement paste and cement mortar datasets. All variables displayed 0% outliers except CNFs (1%) and CS (1%). In addition, it was also observed that the upper outlier percentage for SP and FA had 5% and only 2% for CNFs. Ahmad et al. have also investigated the outliers using a two-layered soft

FIGURE 10 | Concrete multivariate analysis of each variable.

voting-based ensemble model to predict the interfacial tension (IFT) and stated that a higher percentage of outliers may skew the capability of the classifier [55].

Finding patterns and relationships between multiple variables at once is the goal of multivariate analysis [46–48]. When examining complicated datasets, multivariate analysis is particularly helpful as it facilitates a better comprehension of the dataset and its relationship to experimental values. In this study, the multivariate analysis graph was drawn to see the relative frequency distributions. Ayaz et al. have proved that the model's performance was significantly affected by the input variables [50]. Thus, datasets designed are acceptable to develop the ML models for cement-based composites, concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar.

3.6 | Predicting Capability of Models

The developed models were analyzed here to determine the predicting capacity and performance of each model for cement paste,

cement mortar, and concrete. Table 7 presents the results of various performance metrics, including R^2 , MSE, RMSE, MAE, and MAPE, obtained from training and testing datasets for a range of machine learning models, namely Random Forest (RF), Linear Regression (LR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR), AdaBoost Regression (ABR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Bagging Regressor (BR), Extreme Gradient Boosting Regression (XGBR), Decision Tree (DT), and Probabilistic Decision Tree (PDT). These models were utilized to forecast the compressive strength (f_c) of cement paste reinforced with carbon nanofibers (CNFs). Typically, the test dataset error displays the designed model's abstraction capability, whereas the training dataset error assigns the developed model's acceptability. Likewise, the obtained results of metrics for cement mortar and concrete datasets were listed in Tables 8 and 9 respectively.

3.6.1 | Coefficient of Determination

3.6.1.1 | $R^2 > 95\%$. It was listed that the ML algorithms: RF, BR, XGBR, and DT present the coefficient of determination R^2 of

FIGURE 11 | Density curves depicting the input and output parameters of the cement paste dataset.

the train dataset, which is higher than 95%, indicating great correlation with the training data. This shows that the models can perform outstanding calculations of the compressive strength of CNFs reinforced cement-based composites. The test dataset that serves as the basis for the metrics offers a more objective basis for evaluating the predictive power of the RF, BR, XGBR, and DT models while also assisting in the computation of the compressive strength of CNFs [1]. The test dataset R^2 values of the RF, BR, XGBR, and DT models were 0.81, 0.80, 0.79, and 0.79, respectively, which were higher than 0.60, indicating that these models can satisfactorily and accurately determine the compressive strength f_c . It is further demonstrated that those models are acceptable for prediction. This is also seen in that the MSE, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values of these models are much lower.

In Table 6, the DT, XGBR, and RF models developed for cement paste had predicted testing dataset R^2 0.82, 0.82, and 0.76, respectively. Cement mortar in Table 7 determined that the testing dataset R^2 value for RF = 70. In addition, the testing dataset R^2 results of the XGBR, GBR, RF, BR, and DT models for the concrete dataset were 0.93, 0.92, 0.91, 0.90, and 82 respectively, in Table 9.

3.6.1.2 | $R^2 > 90\%$. As can be seen, the R^2 for the algorithms GBR and KNN in the concrete training dataset was better than 90%, indicating good agreement with the training dataset and the ability to determine the compressive strength of CNFs in near proximity to actual values. Based on a comparison of the GBR and KNN models' metrics with the test dataset, these models are

FIGURE 12 | Density curves depicting the input and output parameters of the cement mortar dataset.

significant for prediction because their testing dataset R^2 values are 0.76 and 0.72, respectively, higher than 0.60 [1]. Compressive strength f_c can be satisfactorily and safely predicted with R^2 values larger than 0.60. It is evident that these models' MSE, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values are likewise good. Cement paste had predicted testing dataset R^2 for GBR=0.80 and KNN=0.74 while cement mortar determined GBR = 0.70 and KNN = 0.73. The testing dataset R^2 results of ABR and KNN models for the concrete dataset were 0.91 and 0.86 respectively.

3.6.1.3 | $R^2 > 65\%$. It is evident that the R^2 values in the training dataset for the ABR and PDT models are more than 65%, which is likewise acceptable. While the testing dataset's R^2 value for the PDT model is less than 0.60, which is unacceptable,

the testing dataset's R^2 value for the ABR model is 0.75, which is a significant improvement over the PDT model and whose MSE, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values cannot be disregarded [1]. The testing dataset R^2 results of the SVR model for the concrete dataset were 0.68. Cement paste had a predicted testing dataset R^2 for ABR=0.80 and KNN=0.65, while cement mortar determined KNN = 0.73 and ABR = 0.70.

3.6.1.4 | $R^2 < 65\%$. The LR and SVR regression models are less than 0.60; they demonstrate poor performance and should not be used to assess the compressive strength of CNFs concrete [1, 43]. Compared to other models, these models have greater MSE values. As a result, when it comes to estimating the compressive strength of CNFs reinforced cement-based composites, the

FIGURE 13 | Density curves depicting the input and output parameters of the concrete dataset.

LR and SVR models perform poorly. LR and PDT models failed to predict the compressive strength of the concrete dataset. Also, LR, SVR, and PDT for cement paste and LR, SVR, XGBT, DT, and PDT for the cement mortar dataset were not satisfactory for the prediction of compressive strength f_c .

3.6.1.5 | Best Supervised Regression Models. To compare the performance and predicting capacity of RF, LR, SVR, GBR, ABR, KNN, BR, XGBR, DT, and PDT models for cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete datasets, a comparison graph was drawn. Figure 14 presented the comparison graph of R^2 between the models of results of cement-based composites for the testing dataset. Here, CON, CP, and CM were the abbreviations of concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar, respectively,

and the benchmark of $R^2 = 60\%$. It can be outlined by stating that, according to the results analysis, the XGBR, GBR, and RF models for the concrete dataset; XGBR, DT, and GBR models for the cement paste dataset; and KNN, BR, and RF models for the cement mortar dataset were the best three machine learning models. Hence, these models can be specified as the leading machine learning models.

The compressive strength error graphs can be seen in Figure 15a–c for the testing datasets between actual and predicted values of the XGBR, GBR, and RF models for the concrete dataset; XGBR, DT, and GBR models for the cement paste dataset; and KNN, BR, and RF models for the cement mortar dataset. The XGBR, GBR, and RF models are closer to the prediction line and

TABLE 7 | Capability metrics of each model for cement paste dataset.

No.	Model	Train R^2	Test R^2	K-Fold	MSE	RMSE (Mpa)	MAPE	MAE (Mpa)
1	RF	0.96	0.76	0.76	48.98	6.99	0.103	4.95
2	LR	0.23	0.31	0.31	140.72	11.86	0.212	9.59
3	SVR	0.23	0.31	0.31	140.72	11.86	0.215	9.52
4	GBR	0.93	0.80	0.80	40.08	06.33	0.098	4.63
5	ABR	0.76	0.80	0.63	40.08	06.33	0.097	4.62
6	KNN	0.79	0.65	0.64	71.58	08.46	0.13	6.14
7	BR	0.94	0.74	0.64	71.57	08.45	0.12	6.12
8	XGBR	0.99	0.82	0.82	36.85	6.07	0.09	4.41
9	DT	0.986	0.819	0.68	36.84	6.05	0.085	2.17
10	PDT	0.45	0.34	0.33	83.02	12.45	0.18	8.69

TABLE 8 | Capability metrics of each model for cement mortar dataset.

No.	Model	Train R^2	Test R^2	K-Fold	MSE	RMSE (Mpa)	MAPE	MAE (Mpa)
1	RF	0.96	0.70	0.70	21.88	4.67	0.094	3.63
2	LR	0.39	0.14	0.14	63.51	7.96	0.16	6.14
3	SVR	0.28	0.18	0.18	60.71	7.79	0.16	6.28
4	GBR	0.92	0.70	0.70	21.98	4.69	0.098	4.63
5	ABR	0.76	0.70	0.52	21.98	4.69	0.094	3.48
6	KNN	0.84	0.73	0.72	19.87	4.46	0.095	3.63
7	BR	0.94	0.73	0.66	19.87	4.46	0.095	3.63
8	XGBR	0.99	0.62	0.62	27.82	5.27	0.097	3.75
9	DT	0.998	0.50	0.62	27.81	5.26	0.097	3.74
10	PDT	0.45	0.34	0.33	83.02	12.45	0.18	8.69

TABLE 9 | Capability metrics of each model for concrete dataset.

No.	Model	Train R^2	Test R^2	K-Fold	MSE	RMSE (Mpa)	MAPE	MAE (Mpa)
1	RF	0.966	0.913	0.913	12.44	3.52	0.078	2.38
2	LR	0.820	0.488	0.488	78.53	8.86	0.135	4.16
3	SVR	0.65	0.68	0.67	45.32	6.73	0.165	4.45
4	GBR	0.97	0.92	0.92	11.17	03.34	0.066	2.18
5	ABR	0.91	0.91	0.81	11.18	03.34	0.066	2.17
6	KNN	0.91	0.86	0.85	30.98	05.56	0.108	3.87
7	BR	0.96	0.90	0.78	29.67	05.44	0.108	3.87
8	XGBR	0.98	0.93	0.93	09.77	3.12	0.051	02.14
9	DT	0.98	0.82	0.93	09.66	3.10	0.05	02.17
10	PDT	0.68	0.60	0.58	73.04	08.54	0.16	6.72

similar to the actual f_c dataset values for concrete as compared to the cement paste. Also, the dispersion of data points is very low. It can be identified that the testing dataset prediction values of KNN, BR, and RF models for cement mortar compared to cement paste are not closer to the prediction line and are also not much similar to actual f_c dataset values. The scattering of data points is greater than that of concrete and cement paste models.

In this study, the capability of ten regression models, Random Forest, Linear Regression, Support Vector Regressor, Gradient Boosting Regressor, Ada Boosting Regressor, K-Neighbor Regressor, Bagging Regressor, XG Boost Regressor, Decision Tree, and Pruned Decision Tree to predict the compression strength of concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar for training and test datasets was thoroughly estimated by the metrics: coefficient of

FIGURE 14 | Comparison graph between the models of cement-based composites for testing dataset.

determination, mean absolute percentage error, mean absolute error, mean square error, and root mean square error. However, the coefficient of determination is known as the best of them for model evaluation [11, 13, 49]. According to Nafees et al. and other researchers, if a model's value range falls between 0.60 and 0.75, it is considered acceptable and applicable; if it falls between 0.75 and 0.90, it is considered a good and desired model; and if the value range of the model is greater than 0.95, it indicates excellent projection. R^2 values less than 0.60 [11, 13, 33], however, signify poor performance and undesirable [10, 42, 58]. The results for training datasets proved that: RF, BR, XGBR, and DT models of cement-based composites dataset; XGBR, GBR, RF, BR, and DT models of concrete dataset; DT, XGBR, and RF models developed for cement paste dataset; and RF model of cement mortar dataset had shown $R^2 > 0.95$, and testing datasets also predicted $R^2 > 0.65$.

The testing dataset R^2 results of ABR and KNN models for the concrete dataset were 0.91 and 0.86, respectively. Cement paste had predicted testing dataset R^2 for GBR = 0.80 and BR = 0.74, while cement mortar determined GBR = 0.70 and BR = 0.73. The RMSE, MSE, MAPE, and MAE findings of above-discussed models were also satisfactory [13]. In the end, it can be observed that the training dataset of cement-based composites, R^2 for the models LR and SVR were 0.40 and 0.37, respectively, which failed to predict the compressive strength. LR and PDT models of the concrete dataset; LR, SVR, and PDT for cement paste; and LR, SVR, XGBT, DT, and PDT for the cement mortar dataset were not satisfactory to predict the compressive strength f_c . In our research, it is concluded that the RF model is the one best model for the prediction of compressive strength of concrete and cement paste, which matches with Jesus et al. [13]. The non-resemblance of the estimation performance of every model could be the effect of the number of outliers, number of datapoints, etc. [50, 51]. Overall, the selection of various algorithms was aimed at achieving both computational efficiency and predictive accuracy while addressing dataset characteristics, real-world variability, and model robustness comprehensively.

3.6.2 | Sensitivity Analysis of Compressive Strength

Finding the elements that have the greatest effect on the compressive strength of cellulose nanofiber-reinforced concrete is one of the most important issues that concrete mixture makers may encounter [52]. Since these models have the highest R^2 , the method of sensitivity analysis was applied to the RF, DT, XGBR, GBR, and ABR models in this study to determine if any of the seven independent parameters had a positive effect on the compressive strength of CNFs reinforced cement-based composites, cement paste, cement mortar, and concrete. A technique for figuring out how each independent variable (x) influences the dependent (Y) variable is sensitivity analysis. High sensitivity independent variables have a greater impact on the dependent variable and vice versa. According to an analysis by De-Prado-Gil et al., the parameters that have the biggest effects on the CS of self-compacting concrete are cement and water, which have an impact of 23.47% and 28.39%, respectively, when compared to other variables [13]. Ahmad et al. also calculated that the predictability of concrete's compressive strength was 32% influenced by cement [33]. Hameed et al. investigated the compressive strength of high-performance concrete reinforced with blast furnace slag and fly ash and observed that cement and water had 13.798% and 13.394% feature importance, respectively [52]. The percentage contribution of each variable differs from model to model and type of fibers reinforced [53]. Figure 16 displayed the comparison graph between various types of fibers used by the researchers to reinforce concrete and the percentage contribution to predict the compressive strength.

Therefore, in this research we have conducted the sensitivity analysis test on the above-mentioned five models to compare the feature importance values of each variable. The sensitivity analysis results of concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar variables are listed in Tables 10–12 respectively.

The results of the sensitivity analysis conducted on the RF, DT, XGBR, GBR, and ABR models show that all independent parameters C , W , CNFs, SP, FA, CA, and A have a significant

FIGURE 15 | Scattered plots of Actual vs. Predicted compressive strength of best models for (a) Concrete, (b) Cement paste, and (c) Cement mortar.

and noteworthy impact on the output parameter, which is the compressive strength of concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar with CNFs. The number of independent parameters and datapoints included in the model's execution influences the results of the sensitivity analysis. Additionally, the different percentages of concrete design and the addition of new independent variables alter the analysis's conclusions [54]. Figure 17 shows the notable contribution of coarse aggregate and CNFs independent parameters to output variable in concrete dataset. Furthermore, cement and water in cement paste dataset; and water and age in the cement mortar dataset has

identified remarkable contribution than other independent variables in Figures 18 and 19 respectively.

According to Jesus et al. and Ahmad et al., the sensitivity is the well-known technique to determine the effect of an independent variable on the dependent variable [13, 42, 50]. In this study, the sensitivity analysis was carried out to analyze the feature importance of each input variable on the compressive strength. Jesus et al. have proved in their study that cement 28.39% and water 23.47% displayed the highest contribution in estimating the compressive strength. Ahmad et al. agreed and extended the

FIGURE 16 | Comparative analysis graph of the feature importance.

TABLE 10 | Sensitivity analysis of concrete variables.

Feature	Model			
	RF	DT	XGBR	GBR
C (Kg/m ³)	0.0883	0.0824	0.0326	0.1108
W (Kg/m ³)	0.0335	0.0309	0.0119	0.0204
CNFs (Kg/m ³)	0.2158	0.0619	0.4432	0.2480
SP (Kg/m ³)	0.0277	0.0029	0.0833	0.0303
FA (Kg/m ³)	0.0370	0.0216	0.0121	0.0418
CA (Kg/m ³)	0.4961	0.7290	0.3658	0.0457
A (Day)	0.1014	0.0713	0.0511	0.0920

TABLE 12 | Sensitivity analysis of cement mortar variables.

Feature	Model			
	RF	DT	XGBR	GBR
C (Kg/m ³)	0.1664	0.1257	0.1160	0.1289
W (Kg/m ³)	0.3597	0.3849	0.3801	0.4223
CNFs (Kg/m ³)	0.0784	0.1064	0.1289	0.0601
SP (Kg/m ³)	0.0128	0.0031	0.0000	0.0177
FA (Kg/m ³)	0.1718	0.1304	0.2338	0.1362
A (Day)	0.2110	0.2495	0.1413	0.2348

TABLE 11 | Sensitivity analysis of cement paste variables.

Feature	Model			
	RF	DT	XGBR	GBR
C (Kg/m ³)	0.3605	0.3873	0.4106	0.3748
W (Kg/m ³)	0.4068	0.3795	0.3876	0.4218
CNFs (Kg/m ³)	0.0746	0.0617	0.055	0.075
SP (Kg/m ³)	0.0169	0.0089	0.0434	0.0102
A (Day)	0.1412	0.1626	0.1035	0.1182

work by concluding that cement is a significant factor influencing the prediction of compressive strength [42, 58]. Hameed et al. affirmed that sensitivity analysis is one of the important factors to determine the impact of each variable on compressive strength and concluded that cement had a 13.798% impact [27]. Avinash et al., Tanveer et al., and Tripathi et al. thoroughly described in their research that various models have different importance values for the given features [56, 59, 60]. The results indicated that the cement (34.76%) and the water (36.62%) are

exceedingly important independent parameters in the prediction of compressive strength of CNFs cement-based composites while coarse aggregate has less impact (1.05%) which satisfied the results concluded by the other researchers [1, 13, 42]. In addition, cement (36.05%) and water (40.68%) for cement paste have also shown great contribution to compressive strength. The machine learning models developed in this study can revolutionize concrete construction by optimizing mix proportions, predicting early strength, and ensuring quality control. By accurately predicting compressive strength, engineers can save time, reduce waste, and lower costs by avoiding extensive physical testing. Sensitivity analysis helps prioritize adjustments, while outlier detection identifies potential issues. These models can also be used for research and development, exploring new materials and conducting parametric studies. Successful implementation requires accurate data collection, model training, user-friendly interfaces, and integration with existing systems.

To address the potential issue of overfitting in the machine learning models, a combination of data splitting, cross-validation, hyperparameter tuning, and ensemble methods are investigated. By dividing the dataset into training and testing sets and employing K-fold cross-validation, we ensure the model generalizes well

FIGURE 17 | Sensitivity analysis of the models (a) RF, (b) GBR (c) XGBR, and (d) DT in concrete dataset.

to unseen data. Hyperparameter tuning using random search helps find the optimal balance between model complexity and predictive accuracy. Additionally, ensemble methods like Random Forest and Gradient Boosting Regression improve prediction accuracy and robustness. Sensitivity analysis further aids in identifying influential variables and potential outliers, contributing to a more reliable model. These strategies collectively mitigate the risk of overfitting and enhance the model's predictive performance and generalizability.

4 | Limitations and Future Work

The machine learning models developed in this study have shown promising results in predicting the compressive strength of cement-based composites reinforced with carbon nanofibers (CNFs). However, there are some limitations and potential areas for future research that should be considered. The study focuses on CNFs reinforced cement-based composites, cement paste, and cement mortar. Future research could explore the application of these models to other types of concrete, such as self-compacting concrete, recycled aggregate concrete, and ultra-high performance concrete, to assess their generalizability. The performance of machine learning models heavily depends on the quality and quantity of the dataset used for training. While the current dataset is substantial, it may not fully capture the variability in real-world

applications. Future studies could benefit from larger datasets that include a wider range of mix proportions, environmental conditions, and curing methods. The study employs various machine learning algorithms, but the complexity of these models may not always be necessary for simpler datasets. Future research could investigate the trade-off between model complexity and predictive accuracy to identify more efficient models. While some machine learning models, like decision trees, are inherently interpretable, others, like ensemble methods, can be more difficult to understand. Future research could focus on developing or applying interpretable machine learning techniques to gain insights into the relationships between input parameters and compressive strength.

The selection of hyperparameters can significantly affect the performance of machine learning models. The study uses a systematic approach to select hyperparameters, but there may be more efficient methods, such as Bayesian optimization or genetic algorithms, that could be explored in future research. The study focuses on predicting the compressive strength at various ages. Future research could investigate the long-term performance of the models, especially for predicting the strength of concrete at later ages, which is crucial for durability assessments. While machine learning models can provide accurate predictions, they do not provide a physical understanding of the underlying mechanisms. Future research could explore the integration of

FIGURE 18 | Sensitivity analysis of the models (a) RF, (b) GBR (c) XGBR, and (d) DT in cement paste dataset.

machine learning with physical models to enhance interpretability and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing compressive strength. The study does not consider the environmental impact of the materials used. Future research could incorporate sustainability metrics into the models to assess the environmental footprint of different mix designs. The study focuses on predicting compressive strength but does not consider the economic implications of different mix designs. Future research could include economic analysis to optimize mix designs for cost-effectiveness while maintaining desired strength levels. The study uses a relatively small dataset. Future research could investigate the scalability of the models to larger datasets and more complex scenarios, such as those involving multiple types of fibers or admixtures.

By addressing these limitations and exploring these future research directions, the predictive capabilities of machine learning models for concrete compressive strength can be further improved, leading to more efficient and sustainable concrete mix design and construction practices.

5 | Conclusion

The smaller plant-based particles, cellulose nanofibers, are now utilized to reinforce cement mortar, cement paste, and concrete. However, the examination of experimental strength is costly,

time-consuming, and intricate. Machine learning algorithms are employed to forecast the strength in order to counteract these issues. Nevertheless, the quantity of dataset points also has an impact on the model's prediction value. As a result, the main goals of this work were to compare and estimate the compressive strength of datapoints, which covered three different types of samples: cement paste (266), cement mortar (233), and concrete (196). Seven input variables were taken into consideration as independent parameters in order to predict the compressive strength of CNFs concrete, cement mortar, and cement paste: cement (kg/m^3), water (kg/m^3), CNFs (kg/m^3), superplasticizer (kg/m^3), fine aggregate (kg/m^3), coarse aggregate (kg/m^3), age (Day), and compressive strength f_c (MPa) as dependent variables. Additionally, for the cement paste and cement mortar datasets, respectively, five and six input variables were fixed. Each model's predictive power was evaluated using the following five metrics: R^2 , MSE, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE. Ten models, including RF, LR, SVR, GBR, ABR, KNN, BR, XGBR, DT, and PDT, were applied in this work to project the compressive strength of CNFs concrete, cement paste, and cement mortar. After being obtained, each dataset sample from an experimental study was split into two groups: training (70%) and testing (30%).

The XGBR, GBR, and RF models demonstrated the highest performance accuracy, according to the concrete testing dataset tests. Nevertheless, it was also demonstrated that the compressive strength cannot be accurately predicted by the LR and PDT

FIGURE 19 | Sensitivity analysis of the models (a) RF, (b) GBR (c) XGBR, and (d) DT in cement mortar dataset.

models. For concrete, then, the optimal models are XGBR, GBR, and RF. The XGBR, DT, and GBR models demonstrated the highest performance accuracy, according to the cement paste testing dataset. Nonetheless, it was also demonstrated that the compressive strength cannot be accurately predicted by the LR and SVR models. Therefore, the optimum models for cement paste are XGBR, DT, and GBR.

The cement mortar testing dataset's results indicated that the models with the highest performance accuracy were the RF, BR, and KNN. Nevertheless, it was also demonstrated that the compressive strength cannot be accurately predicted by the LR and SVR models. Hence, XGBR, DT, and GBR are the best models for cement mortar. The sensitivity analysis of the RF, DT, XGBR, GBR, and ABR models reports that cement and water are primary and significant parameters prompting and predicting the compressive strength of CNFs reinforced concrete. Whereas, the coarse aggregate contribution percentage was the minimum valuation. Furthermore, cement and water in the cement paste dataset, and water and age in the cement mortar dataset have identified remarkable contributions than other independent variables. Thus, RF is the one best predicting model of this research.

Author Contributions

Wenyi Yang: writing – original draft, validation, software, methodology, formal analysis, data curation, conceptualization. **Aftab Anwar:** writing – review and editing, visualization, validation, software, resources, methodology, supervision. **Yuanjun Jiang:** writing – review and editing, software. **Wania Naz:** writing – review and editing. **Wang Yanwei:** writing – original draft, visualization, investigation, formal analysis, data curation. **Wang Jing:** writing – original draft, visualization, validation, software, investigation, formal analysis. **Jing Li:** writing – review and editing, visualization, supervision, funding acquisition.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data used to support the findings of this study are included in this published article.

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